

and TMTD, DPG and MBT. In the case of CBS, apart from the general similarities mentioned above, some prominent difference is also noticed in the higher temperature region.

Effect of Antioxidant

Table 2 represents the recipe of the two pairs of systems whose DTA thermograms are shown in Figure 3, curves A and a represent respectively the reclaim compound and that with antioxidant. Curves B and b, on the other hand, stand for the reclaim itself and the same plus antioxidant respectively, whereas curve B' represents the material left after removal of the acetone-extract from the reclaim.*

TABLE 2—FORMULATION OF SYSTEMS** ANALYSED BY DTA

	A	a	B	b
Reclaim	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Stearic acid	0.5	0.5	—	—
Zinc oxide	2.5	2.5	—	—
TMTD††	0.5	0.5	—	—
Sulphur	1.5	1.5	—	—
PBN††	—	0.5	—	0.5

††Tetramethylthiuram disulphide

†† Phenylbetanaphthylamine.

** Formulations are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim.

In the compounds A and a in the region of 140° a break is observed in both the compounds, the break being well-marked and comparatively short respectively in the compounds with and without antioxidant. As per the primary exotherm both in the case of the compound and the reclaim itself there is no appreciable change in the initiation temperature (Ti) on adding the antioxidant to either of the systems, although the pair of compounds have a lower Ti than that of the reclaim. Peak temperature (Tp) also diminishes in the compound as well as in the reclaim base when antioxidant is added to either of them, the compound with and without the antioxidant, however, showing their Tp values to be respectively lower than those the reclaim with and without the same antioxidant. Peak height remains practically unchanged in the compound on addition of antioxidant, which, however, acts quite effectively in the reclaim itself to bring down its peak height. Fractional peak area²⁻⁴ decreases by a small degree in the compound, but appreciably in the reclaim, by using the antioxidant. The antioxidant, however, imparted a much higher change in the peak slope in case of the reclaim than that in the compound based on it.

On the other hand, on separation of the acetone extract from the reclaim, the residual matter exhibits

* Commercial data specifying the reclaim (WTR100) is as follows :

Ash, %	Acetone % Extract,	Carbon % black,	Rubber hydrocarbon by difference, %
10±2	14±4	22±4	Not less than 50

somewhat different characteristics (curve B'). Thus Ti is considerably lowered, Tp is also lowered to some extent. Peak height increases appreciably but peak area is not measured as there is no proper resolution. Moreover, there is no fixed slope from the point of initiation to the peak. The acetone extract is known to contain usually the extender oils (for synthetic hydrocarbons) and process oils (and minor amounts of depolymerized rubber, accelerator, antioxidant residues, etc.).

The portion suggesting a secondary peak above 300° in case of the reclaim does not appear in case of the material left after acetone-extraction. Since the major fraction of the acetone-extract is oil, it may be attributed to the thermal behaviour of the oil (and the rubber). Therefore, on treating the original reclaim with the antioxidant, the nature of the disappearance of this secondary peak may be due mainly to the prevention of the oxidative degradation of the rubber, partly to the thermal degradation of the rubber and partly to the reaction of the antioxidant with the oils present. Similar, but more prominent, elimination of such secondary peak is also observed when the reclaim compound is treated with the antioxidant.

Detailed investigations are in progress and will be published later on.

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References

1. K. K. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1975, 52, 779.
2. K. K. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
3. M. J. VOLD, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 683.
4. J. J. MAURER, *Rubber Chem. Technol.*, 1969, 42, 110.

Metal Complexes of Some β -Ketoimines and Salicylaldimines

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BETA-Ketoimine and salicylaldimine complexes are expected to be similar due to the common O-N donor atom set of each ligand system and the presence of conjugated six-membered chelate ring in them. Recently Holm¹ *et al.* and Yamada² *et al.* have reviewed the metal complexes.

A perusal of the literature has revealed that much work has not been done on anthranilic acid and β -alanine Schiff bases with Benzoylacetone and

o-amino-benzene sulphonic acid Schiff bases with Acetylacetone and Salicylaldehyde. The authors have synthesised four ligands, namely N-Benzoyl-acetoneanthranilic Acid (H_2BA) and N-Benzoyl-acetone- β -alanine ($H_2B\beta A$), *o*-(imine-N-acetylacetone) benzene sulphonic acid (H_2AB) and *o*-(imine-N-salicylidene)benzene sulphonic acid (H_2SB), respectively, by the condensation of respective carbonyl compound with amino compound by the method reported earlier³.

The metal complexes of H_2BA and $H_2B\beta A$ with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) and $UO_2(II)$ were synthesised by the method of Yamada² *et al.* and M. Kubo⁴ *et al.* Their pyridine adducts were synthesised by the method reported earlier³. However, Cu(II) does not form a hydrated complex or the pyridine adduct with H_2BA or $H_2B\beta A$.

Results and Discussion

In general, the metal complexes display 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The Fe(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes may be represented by the formula $[MLX_3]$ where M represents the metal-ion, X stands for H_2O or Py and $LH_2 = H_2BA$ or $H_2B\beta A$. The magnetic moment values show the presence of 4, 3 and 2 unpaired electrons in Fe(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, respectively. The high magnetic moment of Co(II) complexes appear to be due to spin-orbit coupling. The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in dioxan and pyridine were recorded. Each of the spectra of Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II)-complexes in dioxan and pyridine consists of two bands assignable to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ for Co(II)-complexes, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ for Ni(II)-complexes and ${}^2E \rightarrow {}^2T_2$ for the Cu(II) complexes.

However, the Cu(II) complexes exist as a dimer in the solid state. I.R. data of these compounds in

the carbonyl region indicate the presence of anti-symmetric COO^- stretching vibrations ($1580-1595\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the absence of bands around 3650 cm^{-1} and 3250 cm^{-1} due to coordinated molecule of water. This confirms that the Cu(II) complexes are not hydrated ones. These complexes displaying magnetic moments of 1.86 and 1.88 B.M. at 298°K may be represented by a non-planar dimeric structure involving delocalized carboxyl group. The cupric ions may be situated at the opposite ends of an eight-membered ring thereby effectively preventing superexchange.

The metal complexes and the pyridine adducts of Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) and $UO_2(II)$ containing 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry, were found diamagnetic. These data can be explained by assigning a tetrahedral structure for the Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes, a square-planar configuration for the Pd(II) complexes and an octahedral structure for the $UO_2(II)$ complexes.

From these results it is evident that the general similarity of the complexes of H_2BA and $H_2B\beta A$ is due to the presence in them of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in β -position to the carboxyl group.

Stabilities of H_2AB and H_2SB Complexes

H_2AB and H_2SB contain sulphonic, enolic or phenolic hydroxyl and imino groups and are thus biprotic tridentates. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of these ligands were found by Algebraic and Bjerrum's modified method⁵. The average value of pK_1 and pK_2 for H_2AB and H_2SB were found 2.54 and 8.97 and 2.05 and 8.13 respectively.

The metal-ligand stability constants were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique^{6,7}. The approximate values of stability constants were read directly from formation curve using Bjerrum

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANT OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH H_2SB AND H_2AB .

		Temperature = $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$						$\mu = 0.1M\ NaClO_4$					
Methods		H_2SB -complexes						H_2AB -complexes					
		$UO_2(II)$	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)	$UO_2(II)$	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)
A	log K_1	7.00	6.43	5.97	5.73	2.69	0.82	8.175	7.100	6.125	5.550	4.250	3.500
	log K_2	5.73	4.72	3.96	3.76	—	—	5.625	4.100	2.575	2.250	—	—
B	log K_1	7.05	6.45	5.98	5.75	—	—	8.125	7.000	6.120	5.610	—	—
	log K_2	5.70	4.70	3.95	3.75	—	—	5.695	4.200	2.590	2.250	—	—
C	log K_1	7.05	4.46	5.97	5.74	—	—	8.178	7.101	6.125	5.5506	—	—
	log K_2	5.55	4.68	3.89	3.72	—	—	5.621	4.098	2.574	2.2494	—	—
D	log K_1	7.10	6.41	6.00	5.80	—	—	8.175	7.100	6.125	5.550	—	—
	log K_2	5.72	4.72	4.00	3.80	—	—	5.625	4.100	2.575	2.250	—	—
E	log K_1	7.05	6.43	5.98	5.76	2.69	0.82	8.163	7.075	6.123	5.565	4.250	3.500
	log K_2	5.66	4.70	3.95	3.76	—	—	5.644	4.124	2.578	2.250	—	—
ΔF	—	17.41	15.47	13.62	13.06	3.692	1.125	18.97	13.43	11.94	10.72	5.833	4.804

where A = Interpolation at half n values method;
 C = Successive approximation method;
 E = Mean values;

B = Interpolation at various n values method;
 D = Convergence formula method;
 ΔF = Overall free energy change k.cal/mole.

half $\bar{n}$ method⁶. Refinement of the approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was done by different computational methods⁸. The results thus obtained are summarized in Table I in which the values of overall free energy changes accompanying the complexation reactions have also been included.

It is evident from the data presented in Table I that the stability constants of these complexes are in the order $UO_2 > Cu > Ni > Co > Zn > Cd$, which is in agreement with the Irving and Williams rule⁹.

References

1. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT (JR.) and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 88.
2. S. YAMADA, Y. KUGE and K. YAMANOUCHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 40, 1864.
3. R. K. MEHTA, S. P. RAO and R. C. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 933.
4. M. KUBO, Y. KURODA, M. KISHITA and Y. MUTO, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1963, 16, 7.
5. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5052.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
7. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
8. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
9. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.

Some Crystal Field Surface Orbital—Bond Energy Bond Order (CFSO-BEBO) Calculations of Heats of Adsorption of Hydrogen on Nickel Methanation Catalysts

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THE production of methane on nickel catalyst has gained an impetus in recent years on account of its importance in the production of S.N.G. (synthetic natural gas). For example, a methane synthesis unit has been attached to Westfield Lurgi Plant¹ for enrichment of the gas produced by the high pressure process.

Some adsorption studies of hydrogen on nickel catalyst were carried out, and a few isosteric heats of adsorption calculated by the author² some years ago. The advent of crystal field surface orbital bond energy bond order (CFSO-BEBO) model³ has facilitated the theoretical calculation of heats of adsorption. Although the calculations lack the usefulness of other theoretical treatments, such as Extended Huckel⁴, they nevertheless provide a simple theoretical model (involving as they do a combination of crystal field theory, crystal symmetry and Born-Haber Cycle concepts) which is able to explain experimental results. The heats of adsorption (both molecular and chemisorption) of hydrogen on platinum calculated by the CFSO-BEBO procedure have been found to agree very well with those

determined experimentally. Further, the variation of heat of adsorption as a function of coverage has been placed on a theoretical basis.

The catalysts, based on nickel were prepared by precipitation on Kieselguhr from solutions of their nitrates. They had the composition given below:

Catalyst C : Nickel : Thoria : Kieselguhr
: : 100 : 18 : 100.

Catalyst D : Nickel : Thoria : Chromium Oxide :
Kieselguhr : : 100 : 9 : 9 : 100

The adsorption of hydrogen was carried out as described previously², in a volumetric gas adsorption apparatus. The heats of adsorption were calculated from the isotherms at temperatures specified in Table I.

TABLE I—COMPARISON OF HEATS OF MOLECULAR CHEMISORPTION COMPUTED ON CFSO-BEBO MODEL* AND BY ISOSTERIC METHOD ON NICKEL CATALYSTS C AND D

Catalyst	Heats of absorption, Cals/Mole	
	on CFSO-BEBO Model	Isosteric Method
C. Nickel-thoria-kieselguhr	3.2 to 3.8	3.6 to 4.4
D. Nickel-thoria-chromium oxide-kieselguhr.	,,	6.4 to 7.1

* Values calculated at bond order $\eta_{H-H} = 0.116$ (or H-H distance = 1.737 Å) and $\eta = 0$ on the basis of Ni-Ni bond energy⁵ of 34.2 k.cal/mole.

The heats of adsorption calculated theoretically by the CFSO-BEBO model for hydrogen on nickel are given in Table I. Nickel was assumed to have a structure isoelectronic with platinum ($3d^7 4sp^2$, with e_g and t_{2g} adsorption sites) and of the same symmetry as platinum. The separation between 2e_g and $2t_{2g}$ sites on nickel (111) is 2.48 Å (compared with 2.77 Å for platinum) and the separation between an e_g and an t_{2g} site of nickel is 1.44 Å (as against 1.60 Å for platinum)⁵.

The agreement between the values, in the case of catalyst C); is good considering the assumptions involved viz., (a) the Ni-Ni distances are the same in the catalyst as in pure metal, (b) the heat² of physical adsorption of hydrogen on nickel is 18 k.cals/mole i.e., same as on Pt. It is however, too much to expect a close agreement in the case of the more composite Catalyst D.

Note :

The views expressed in this short note are those of the author, and not of the Institute.

References

1. *Chem. Eng. News*, Aug. 1974, 18.
2. K. A. KINI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (in press).
- 2a. J. C. GHOSH, M. V. C. SASTRI and K. A. KINI, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1952, 44, 2463.